

Smooth Variational Diffusion and Signal-to-Noise Ratio Equivalence

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Abstract

Common diffusion generative models rely on stochastic processes with trajectories that are almost nowhere differentiable. This work is a proof of concept in which we construct a diffusion generative process whose trajectories are always differentiable. To do so, we use a two-dimensional Gaussian process in which one dimension is the derivative of the other. Building on prior phase-space diffusion approaches such as Critically-Damped Langevin Diffusion (Dockhorn et al., 2022) and the Acceleration Generative Model (Chen et al., 2023), we (i) consider a fully general second-order SDE with arbitrary time-dependent coefficients, and (ii) derive an exact ELBO in phase space. As a consequence, we show that the diffusion loss depends only on a scalar signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), which fully decouples the training of the denoising model from the parameterization of the noising process. The code illustrating the approach can be found [here](#).

1. Introduction

This work is a proof of concept in which we present a diffusion generative model with differentiable trajectories. It is based on a rather general SDE that preserves the Gaussian property.

We take advantage of the infinite time formulation of the diffusion loss and give formulas for the exact ELBO, without reliance on the score matching approach common to SDE models ([1]).

Augmenting the state with a velocity variable has been explored before, we discuss prior work in Section 2. Our construction differs in two ways: we allow the second-order linear SDE to have arbitrary time-dependent coefficients, and we derive an exact ELBO in the continuous-time limit. The resulting bound depends only on a scalar signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), so the denoising model can be trained independently of the process parameterization, including reuse of pretrained one-dimensional models.

We perform simple experiments illustrating our methods and present the code for them, along with a description of an algorithm for the fast numerical calculation of process parameters.

2. Related Work

Diffusion generative models were originally formulated as denoising processes in the data space and trained either through a variational lower bound [2] or through denoising score matching [1]. [3] reformulated training through a variational lower bound (VDM) and showed that, in the continuous-time limit, the diffusion loss depends only on the signal-to-noise ratio. Our work directly extends this ELBO-based viewpoint from the one-dimensional state space to a phase-space setting.

Diffusion generative modeling has rapidly diversified since its original variational [2] and score-based [1] formulations. Notable recent directions include the EDM design space [4], flow matching and rectified flow ([5], [6]), and consistency models for few-step sampling ([7]). Our contribution lies in a more specialized direction, phase-space diffusion, where the state is augmented with a velocity variable.

The idea of augmenting the state with an auxiliary velocity variable was introduced by Critically-Damped Langevin Diffusion (CLD [8]), which couples position and velocity through a Hamiltonian-inspired SDE with fixed scalar coefficients and is trained via hybrid score matching. The Acceleration Generative Model (AGM [9]) replaces score matching with a phase-space stochastic bridge derived from stochastic optimal control, allowing time-varying diffusion coefficient but keeping the structure of linear momentum dynamics.

Our SDE generalizes both CLD and AGM by treating all SDE coefficients as free time-dependent functions. CLD is recovered as the constant-coefficient critical-damping case. In contrast to the score-

matching and bridge-matching objectives used in those works, we derive an exact ELBO in phase space. In the continuous-time limit, the resulting diffusion loss reduces to a scalar SNR term, extending the one-dimensional result of to the phase-space setting.

3. Preliminaries

For a proper introduction to diffusion models, please refer to [3]. We will use similar notation. Here we briefly discuss the most important results for us from [3].

Having data distribution $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x})$, a Gaussian process is constructed with latent variables $\mathbf{z}_t, t \in [0, 1]$ with density conditioned on \mathbf{x} being

$$\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_t|\mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{N}(\alpha_t \mathbf{x}, \beta_t \mathbf{I}) \quad (1)$$

where α_t and β_t are predefined positive functions of t . They are often chosen so that $\alpha_t^2 = 1 - \beta_t$ to preserve variance. All of the $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_t|\mathbf{z}_s)$ and $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_s|\mathbf{z}_t, \mathbf{x})$ are Gaussian. The process is also Markov. Sometimes we will drop the identity matrix from the normal distribution covariance notation for simplicity.

The generative model is built by inverting the process and generating latent variables from $t = 0$ to $t = 1$.

If the interval $[0, 1]$ is evenly divided by T parts, all having the length $\tau = \frac{1}{T}$, then the loss L_{vib} of this model is the negative Evidence Lower Bound (ELBO) that bounds the likelihood of the data:

$$\begin{aligned} -\log \mathbf{p}(x) \leq L_{\text{vib}} = & \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_0|\mathbf{x})}(-\log \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}_0)) + \mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_1|\mathbf{x}) \| \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{z}_1)) + \\ & \sum_{i=0}^{T-1} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_{(i+1)\tau}|\mathbf{x})} \mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_{i\tau}|\mathbf{z}_{(i+1)\tau}, \mathbf{x}) \| \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{z}_{i\tau}|\mathbf{z}_{(i+1)\tau})) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The first term is the reconstruction loss. A simple approach here is to have \mathbf{z}_0 being equal to $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{z}_0; \mathbf{x}_0, \delta)$, where δ is some small value. Then, if we choose $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}_0) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{z}_0, \delta)$, this term can be computed analytically. By lowering δ it can be made arbitrarily close to $-\infty$, but this will harm the last term of the loss, so some balance needs to be found. The second term is the prior loss. It is also analytically computable.

The last term is the diffusion loss (L_{diff}). $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{z}_{i\tau}|\mathbf{z}_{(i+1)\tau})$ is chosen as

$$\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{z}_{i\tau}|\mathbf{z}_{(i+1)\tau}) = \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_{i\tau}|\mathbf{z}_{(i+1)\tau}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\theta}(\mathbf{z}((i+1)\tau), (i+1)\tau)) \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\theta}(\mathbf{z}((i+1)\tau), (i+1)\tau)$ is modelled by a neural network with parameters θ . It can be simplified to the following expression

$$L_{\text{diff}} = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), i \sim U\{0, T-1\}} \frac{\mathcal{S}_{(i+1)\tau} - \mathcal{S}_{i\tau}}{\tau} \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\theta}(\mathbf{z}(i+1)\tau, (i+1)\tau)\|_2^2 \quad (4)$$

meaning that the expectation is taken over all time indices and over noise generating \mathbf{z}_t . \mathcal{S}_t here is the signal-to-noise ratio, which in the one-dimensional case is equal to $\frac{\alpha_t^2}{\beta_t}$.

In [3] it was shown that the more steps the process has, the better the loss. If we take the limit $T \rightarrow \infty$, then L_{diff} becomes

$$L_{\text{diff}}^{\infty} = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), t \sim U[0, 1]} \mathcal{S}'_t \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\theta}(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \quad (5)$$

This is the key step that will be used in our following construction. Since the limit is taken, what matters are only the main terms of the sum in Equation 2.

4. Smooth Process Construction

Let $\mathbf{x} \sim \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x})$ be the data distribution. Without loss of generality in this text we assume $\mathbb{E}\mathbf{x} = 0, \mathbb{D}\mathbf{x} = 1$. Next, $\mathbf{u}_t, t \in [0, 1]$ will be our “noising” process. We will construct it by first defining its derivative and then integrating it.

Let $\mathbf{z}_t = (\mathbf{u}_t, \mathbf{v}_t)$, $t \in [0, 1]$ be a stochastic process that satisfies the following system of SDEs:

$$\begin{aligned} d\mathbf{u}_t &= \mathbf{v}_t dt \\ d\mathbf{v}_t &= -r_t \mathbf{u}_t dt - f_t \mathbf{v}_t dt + g_t d\mathbf{w}_t \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Here \mathbf{w}_t is a Wiener process and r_t, f_t, g_t are deterministic continuous functions on $[0, 1]$ ($g_t > 0$). We will call \mathbf{v}_t the velocity of the process and \mathbf{u}_t the location. Intuitively, the functions r_t and f_t regulate how much influence location and velocity have on the stochastic acceleration of our process. The minuses before these terms are chosen so that we can think of r_t and f_t as “zero-reverting” forces.

Equation 6 generalizes the SDE used in CLD ([8]), where r_t, f_t, g_t are restricted to constants, and the AGM construction ([9]), which allows time-varying g_t but keeps r_t and f_t fixed by the linear-momentum bridge structure. By keeping all three coefficients as free time-dependent functions we lose the closed-form solution available in those settings, but we gain the flexibility to shape the entire SNR trajectory at training time, which we exploit in Section 6.

We want to mention that in this setting it is enough to use the Wiener integral construction [10], without relying on the more general stochastic integral, which requires an interpretation (Ito, Stratonovich).

We would like to know the global evolution of the parameters of this process so that we can sample intermediate points from it for training. Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\mathbf{u}_t &= \mathbf{x}\boldsymbol{\alpha}_t \\ \mathbb{E}\mathbf{v}_t &= \mathbf{x}\boldsymbol{\lambda}_t \\ \mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}_t &= \boldsymbol{\nu}_t \\ \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_t &= \boldsymbol{\beta}_t \\ \text{cov}(\mathbf{u}_t, \mathbf{v}_t) &= \boldsymbol{\kappa}_t \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Here we assume \mathbf{x} to be fixed, i.e., all parameters are meant to be conditioned on \mathbf{x} .

4.1. Velocity

By definition Equation 6 means that $\forall \tau$

$$\mathbf{v}_{t+\tau} = \mathbf{v}_t + \int_t^{t+\tau} (-r_s \mathbf{u}_s - f_s \mathbf{v}_s) ds + \int_t^{t+\tau} g_s d\mathbf{w}_s \quad (8)$$

Since g_t is a non-random function, the last (stochastic) integral can be well-defined using the Wiener integral (see [10]). This integral has zero mean and variance $\int_t^{t+\tau} g_s^2 ds$.

Under the above conditions on f_t, r_t and g_t , Equation 8 has a unique solution. Since the coefficient of ds is linear in \mathbf{z}_t , and g_t is non-random, this solution is a Gaussian process (for the proof, see, for example, Chapter 8.2 in [11]). It will also be mean-square continuous (Section 7.1.5 in [11]), that is

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow 0} \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{v}_{t+\tau} - \mathbf{v}_t)^2 = 0 \quad (9)$$

In this work, analogous to $o(\cdot)$ -notation, this property will be written as $\mathbf{v}_{t+\tau} \stackrel{\tau \rightarrow 0}{=} \mathbf{v}_t + \{\!\!\{1\}\!\!\}$ or simply $\mathbf{v}_{t+\tau} = \mathbf{v}_t + \{\!\!\{1\}\!\!\}$. The last term (in curly brackets) represents a Gaussian variable (a stochastic process of τ) that diminishes at zero faster than the function in brackets. Appendix A gives a definition and properties of such processes that we will need.

Then, setting $u = s - t$

$$\mathbf{v}_{t+\tau} = \mathbf{v}_t - \int_0^\tau (r_t + o(1))(\mathbf{u}_t + \{\!\!\{1\}\!\!\}) du - \int_0^\tau (f_t + o(1))(\mathbf{v}_t + \{\!\!\{1\}\!\!\}) du + \int_t^{t+\tau} g_s d\mathbf{w}_s = \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_t - r_t \mathbf{u}_t \tau - f_t \mathbf{v}_t \tau + \{\!\!\{\tau^2\}\!\!\} + o(\tau) + \int_t^{t+\tau} g_s d\mathbf{w}_s = \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_t - r_t \mathbf{u}_t \tau - f_t \mathbf{v}_t \tau + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) + \{\tau^2\} \quad (12)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) = \int_t^{t+\tau} g_s d\mathbf{w}_s$ is a Gaussian process with zero mean and variance $G_t(\tau) = \int_t^{t+\tau} g_s^2 ds$. Also, $\text{cov}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\sigma), \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau)) = G_t(\min(\sigma, \tau))$. Note that $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) \in \llbracket \tau \rrbracket$. The process $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau)$ is independent of \mathbf{v}_t .

Mean:

$$\mathbf{x} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_{t+\tau} = \mathbf{x} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_t (1 - f_t \tau) - r_t \mathbf{x} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_t \tau + o(\tau) \Rightarrow \quad (13)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}'_t = -f_t \boldsymbol{\lambda}_t - r_t \boldsymbol{\alpha}_t \quad (14)$$

Variance:

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_{t+\tau} = \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v}_t(1 - \tau f_t) - \tau \mathbf{u}_t r_t + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) + \{\tau^2\}) = \quad (15)$$

$$\text{cov}(\mathbf{v}_t(1 - \tau f_t) - \tau \mathbf{u}_t r_t + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) + \{\tau^2\}, \mathbf{v}_t(1 - \tau f_t) - \tau \mathbf{u}_t r_t + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) + \{\tau^2\}) = \quad (16)$$

$$\text{cov}(\mathbf{v}_t(1 - \tau f_t) - \tau \mathbf{u}_t r_t, \mathbf{v}_t(1 - \tau f_t) - \tau \mathbf{u}_t r_t) + G_t(\tau) + o(\tau) = \quad (17)$$

$$(1 - \tau f_t)^2 \boldsymbol{\nu}_t + \tau^2 r_t^2 \boldsymbol{\beta}_t - 2\tau(1 - \tau f_t) r_t \boldsymbol{\kappa}_t + G_t(\tau) + o(\tau) = \quad (18)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}_t - 2\tau f_t \boldsymbol{\nu}_t - 2\tau r_t \boldsymbol{\kappa}_t + G_t(\tau) + o(\tau) \Rightarrow \quad (19)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}'_t = -2f_t \boldsymbol{\nu}_t - 2r_t \boldsymbol{\kappa}_t + g_t^2 \quad (20)$$

4.2. Location

Now we want to integrate \mathbf{v}_t locally once again (“once again”, because \mathbf{v}_t is an SDE solution):

$$\mathbf{v}_{t+u} = \mathbf{v}_t - r_t \mathbf{u}_t u - f_t \mathbf{v}_t u + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(u) + \{u^2\} \quad (21)$$

Integrate by u , assuming $\mathbf{u}'_t = \mathbf{v}_t$:

$$\int_0^\tau \mathbf{v}_{t+u} du = \int_0^\tau (\mathbf{v}_t - r_t \mathbf{u}_t u - f_t \mathbf{v}_t u + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(u) + \{u^2\}) du \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{t+\tau} - \mathbf{u}_t = \mathbf{v}_t \tau - \frac{1}{2} r_t \tau^2 \mathbf{u}_t - \frac{1}{2} f_t \tau^2 \mathbf{v}_t + \{\tau^4\} + \int_0^\tau \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) d\tau \quad (23)$$

Let us look at the last integral and name it $\boldsymbol{\eta}_t(\tau)$. It is a Gaussian process (since integration is a linear operation) and it has zero mean. Let’s find its variance and covariance with $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t$.

Define $\mathcal{G}_t(\tau) = \int_t^{t+\tau} G_t(s) ds$, and $\mathfrak{G}_t(\tau) = \int_t^{t+\tau} \mathcal{G}_t(s) ds$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{cov}(\boldsymbol{\eta}_t(\tau), \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau)) &= \mathbb{E} \left(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) \int_0^\tau \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(u) du \right) = \mathbb{E} \left(\int_0^\tau \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(u) du \right) = \\ & \int_0^\tau \mathbb{E}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(u)) du = \int_0^\tau G_t(u) du = \mathcal{G}_t(\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Variance:

$$\mathbb{D}[\boldsymbol{\eta}_t(\tau)] = \mathbb{E} \left(\int_0^\tau \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(u) du \right)^2 = \int_0^\tau \int_0^\tau \mathbb{E}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(u) \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(v)) du dv = \quad (25)$$

$$\int_0^\tau \int_0^\tau G_t(\min(u, v)) du dv = \quad (26)$$

$$\int_0^\tau \left(\int_0^v G_t(u) du + G_t(v) \int_v^\tau 1 du \right) dv = \quad (27)$$

$$\int_0^\tau (\mathcal{G}_t(v) + (\tau - v)G_t(v)) dv = \quad (28)$$

$$\mathfrak{G}_t(\tau) + \tau \int_0^\tau G_t(v) dv - \int_0^\tau vG_t(v) dv = \quad (29)$$

$$\mathfrak{G}_t(\tau) + \tau \mathcal{G}_t(\tau) - \left(\tau \mathcal{G}_t(\tau) - \int_0^\tau \mathcal{G}_t(v) dv \right) = \quad (30)$$

$$2\mathfrak{G}_t(\tau) \quad (31)$$

So we get

$$\mathbf{u}_{t+\tau} = \mathbf{u}_t + \mathbf{v}_t\tau - \frac{1}{2}r_t\tau^2\mathbf{u}_t - \frac{1}{2}f_t\tau^2\mathbf{v}_t + \boldsymbol{\eta}_t(\tau) + \{\tau^4\} \quad (32)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\eta}_t(\tau) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 2\mathfrak{G}_t(\tau)) \quad (33)$$

Note that $\boldsymbol{\eta}_t(\tau) \in \llbracket \tau^3 \rrbracket$ and does not depend on \mathbf{u}_t and \mathbf{v}_t .

Now we want to obtain an ODE for the mean and variance of \mathbf{u}_t , and for the covariance between \mathbf{u}_t and \mathbf{v}_t . For this it will be enough to use only the linear terms:

$$\mathbf{u}_{t+\tau} = \mathbf{u}_t + \mathbf{v}_t\tau + \boldsymbol{\eta}_t(\tau) + \llbracket \tau^4 \rrbracket \quad (34)$$

Mean:

$$\mathbf{x}\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{t+\tau} = \mathbf{x}\boldsymbol{\alpha}_t + \mathbf{x}\boldsymbol{\lambda}_t\tau + o(\tau^2) \Rightarrow \quad (35)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}'_t = \boldsymbol{\lambda}_t \quad (36)$$

Variance:

$$\boldsymbol{\beta}_{t+\tau} = \boldsymbol{\beta}_t + \tau^2\boldsymbol{\nu}_t + O(\tau^3) + O(\tau^4) + 2\tau\boldsymbol{\kappa}_t + O(\tau^{\frac{7}{2}}) + O(\tau^3) + O(\tau^2) \Rightarrow \quad (37)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\beta}'_t = 2\boldsymbol{\kappa}_t \quad (38)$$

Here on the right side are the orders of covariations between each pair of the terms (omitting zeros). See Appendix A for details.

Covariance:

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa}_{t+\tau} = \mathbb{E}((\mathbf{u}_{t+\tau} - \mathbb{E}\mathbf{u}_{t+\tau})(\mathbf{v}_{t+\tau} - \mathbb{E}\mathbf{v}_{t+\tau})) = \quad (39)$$

$$\mathbb{E}(((\mathbf{u}_t - \mathbb{E}\mathbf{u}_t) + (\mathbf{v}_t - \mathbb{E}\mathbf{v}_t)\tau + \boldsymbol{\eta}_t(\tau) + \llbracket \tau^4 \rrbracket) \times ((\mathbf{v}_t - \mathbb{E}\mathbf{v}_t)(1 - f_t\tau) - r_t\tau(\mathbf{u}_t - \mathbb{E}\mathbf{u}_t) + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) + \{\tau^2\})) = \quad (40)$$

$$\mathbb{E}(((\mathbf{u}_t - \mathbb{E}\mathbf{u}_t) + (\mathbf{v}_t - \mathbb{E}\mathbf{v}_t)\tau) \times ((\mathbf{v}_t - \mathbb{E}\mathbf{v}_t)(1 - f_t\tau) - r_t\tau(\mathbf{u}_t - \mathbb{E}\mathbf{u}_t))) + o(\tau) = \quad (41)$$

$$(1 - f_t\tau)\boldsymbol{\kappa}_t - r_t\tau\boldsymbol{\beta}_t + \tau\boldsymbol{\nu}_t + o(\tau) \Rightarrow \quad (42)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa}'_t = -f_t\boldsymbol{\kappa}_t - r_t\boldsymbol{\beta}_t + \boldsymbol{\nu}_t \quad (43)$$

Now we have a set of ODEs that define the evolution of the process:

$$\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\alpha}'_t = \boldsymbol{\lambda}_t \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}'_t = -f_t\boldsymbol{\lambda}_t - r_t\boldsymbol{\alpha}_t \\ \boldsymbol{\beta}'_t = 2\boldsymbol{\kappa}_t \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}'_t = \boldsymbol{\nu}_t - f_t\boldsymbol{\kappa}_t - r_t\boldsymbol{\beta}_t \\ \boldsymbol{\nu}'_t = g_t^2 - 2f_t\boldsymbol{\nu}_t - 2r_t\boldsymbol{\kappa}_t \end{cases} \quad (44)$$

Given the initial conditions and knowing f_t, r_t and g_t , the evolution of all the parameters is defined. This is a system of linear non-stationary ODEs. Analytical solutions generally do not exist, so we will not be able to freely “draw” a path of β_t and α_t as in the one-dimensional case. Instead, we will parameterize f_t, r_t and g_t with neural networks and solve Equation 44 numerically.

Generally, numerical iterations can create a time bottleneck, but in Appendix G we present an algorithm that parallelizes the evaluation process, making it considerably faster.

5. Variational Inference

5.1. Local Formulation

We have:

$$\mathbf{v}_{t+\tau} = \mathbf{v}_t - r_t \mathbf{u}_t \tau - f_t \mathbf{v}_t \tau + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) + \{\tau^2\} \quad (45)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t(\tau) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, G_t(\tau)) \quad (46)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{t+\tau} = \mathbf{u}_t + \mathbf{v}_t \tau - \frac{1}{2} r_t \tau^2 \mathbf{u}_t - \frac{1}{2} f_t \tau^2 \mathbf{v}_t + \boldsymbol{\eta}_t(\tau) + \{\tau^4\} \quad (47)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\eta}_t(\tau) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 2\mathcal{G}_t(\tau)) \quad (48)$$

Since g_t is continuous, all its integrals can be locally approximated as:

$$G_t(\tau) = g^2(t)\tau + o(\tau)$$

$$\mathcal{G}_t(\tau) = \frac{1}{2}g^2(t)\tau^2 + o(\tau^2) \quad (49)$$

$$\mathcal{G}_t(\tau) = \frac{1}{6}g^2(t)\tau^3 + o(\tau^3)$$

5.2. Normal Posterior

Let $\mathbf{z}_t = (\mathbf{u}_t, \mathbf{v}_t)^T$, $\tau = t - s$, $s < t$.

Global mean and covariance matrix:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_s = \mathbf{x} \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \end{pmatrix} \quad (50)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s = \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\beta}_s & \boldsymbol{\kappa}_s \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa}_s & \boldsymbol{\nu}_s \end{pmatrix} \quad (51)$$

So,

$$\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_s | \mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_s, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s) \quad (52)$$

Locally:

$$\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_t | \mathbf{z}_s, \mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t|s}) \quad (53)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s} = \begin{pmatrix} (1 - \frac{1}{2}r_s\tau^2)\mathbf{u}_s + (\tau - \frac{1}{2}f_s\tau^2)\mathbf{v}_s \\ -\tau r_s \mathbf{u}_s + (1 - f_s\tau)\mathbf{v}_s \end{pmatrix} + o\left(\begin{matrix} \tau^2 \\ \tau \end{matrix}\right) \quad (54)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t|s} = g_s^2 \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3}\tau^3 & \frac{1}{2}\tau^2 \\ \frac{1}{2}\tau^2 & \tau \end{pmatrix} + o\left(\begin{matrix} \tau^3 & \tau^2 \\ \tau^2 & \tau \end{matrix}\right) \quad (55)$$

Define

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \frac{1}{2}r_s\tau^2 & \tau - \frac{1}{2}f_s\tau^2 \\ -r_s\tau & 1 - f_s\tau \end{pmatrix} + o\left(\begin{matrix} \tau^2 & \tau^2 \\ \tau & \tau \end{matrix}\right) \quad (56)$$

So that,

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{z}_s \quad (57)$$

Then:

$$\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_t|\mathbf{z}_s, \mathbf{x}) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{z}_s, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t|s}) \quad (58)$$

In Appendix B we infer the mean and covariance matrix of the posterior distribution $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_s|\mathbf{z}_t, \mathbf{x})$:

$$\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_s|\mathbf{z}_t, \mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t}) \quad (59)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t}(\mathbf{H}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{z}_t + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s) \quad (60)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t} = (\mathbf{H}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1})^{-1} \quad (61)$$

5.3. Diffusion Loss

Now we need to calculate the KL divergence between the true and predicted posteriors in Equation 2. As is common in diffusion models, for the predicted posterior we will use the same formula as for the true posterior, but instead of \mathbf{x} we will use the prediction of the network $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)$. Then:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_s = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \end{pmatrix} \quad (62)$$

The KL divergence then becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(s) &:= \mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_s|\mathbf{z}_t, \mathbf{x}) \| \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{z}_s|\mathbf{z}_t)) = \\ &\frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{s|t})^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t}^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{s|t}) \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

Difference of means:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{s|t} &= \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t}(\mathbf{H}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{z}_t + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s) - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t}(\mathbf{H}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{z}_t + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_s) = \\ &\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t}(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_s) = \\ &\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_s) \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

Substituting:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(s) &= \\ &\frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_s))^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_s) = \\ &\frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_s)^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_s) = \\ &\frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \left(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \end{pmatrix} \right)^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t} \left(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \end{pmatrix} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

Here we are interested in the asymptotically main term. In our context, we are looking for the term with the lowest degree of τ . If A is some matrix that depends on τ (in our case each element is a rational function of τ), we will write $[A]$ to represent its asymptotically main part: for each element of A , only the term with the lowest degree is retained. Refer to Appendix C for details and properties of this operation.

Since in the $\mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(s)$ expression only $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t}$ depends on τ , then:

$$[\mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(s)] = \left[\frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \left(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \end{pmatrix} \right)^T [\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t}] \left(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \end{pmatrix} \right) \right] \quad (66)$$

In Appendix D we show that

$$[\mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(s)] = \tau \frac{g_s^2}{2} \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \boldsymbol{\kappa}_s - \boldsymbol{\beta}_s \boldsymbol{\lambda}_s}{\boldsymbol{\beta}_s \boldsymbol{\nu}_s - \boldsymbol{\kappa}_s^2} \right)^2 \quad (67)$$

Now summing over all the terms in the last part of Equation 2:

$$[L_{\text{diff}}] = \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), t \sim U\{0, T-1\}} g_s^2 \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \boldsymbol{\kappa}_s - \boldsymbol{\beta}_s \boldsymbol{\lambda}_s}{\boldsymbol{\beta}_s \boldsymbol{\nu}_s - \boldsymbol{\kappa}_s^2} \right)^2 \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \quad (68)$$

Now if we take the limit $T \rightarrow \infty$ then $t \rightarrow s$, and the main part of L_{diff} is all that is left, so finally (assuming $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)$ is continuous):

$$L_{\text{diff}}^\infty = \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), t \sim U[0, 1]} g_t^2 \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\alpha}_t \boldsymbol{\kappa}_t - \boldsymbol{\beta}_t \boldsymbol{\lambda}_t}{\boldsymbol{\beta}_t \boldsymbol{\nu}_t - \boldsymbol{\kappa}_t^2} \right)^2 \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \quad (69)$$

5.4. Generative Step

We have computed the main term of the loss, but at generation time we will perform steps that will generate data from noise. It is obvious that the main term of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t}$ is \mathbf{z}_t . We are interested in the main term of the step $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} - \mathbf{z}_t$.

In Appendix E we show that for the generative step, its main term of the mean is

$$\tau \left(r_s \mathbf{u}_t + f_s \mathbf{v}_t + \frac{g_s^2}{\boldsymbol{\beta}_s \boldsymbol{\nu}_s - \boldsymbol{\kappa}_s^2} (-\boldsymbol{\kappa}_s (\boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{u}_t) + \boldsymbol{\beta}_s (\boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{v}_t)) \right) \quad (70)$$

and for the covariance matrix we will use

$$[\mathbf{H}]^{-1} [\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t|s}] [\mathbf{H}^{-T}] = g_s^2 \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3} \tau^3 & -\frac{1}{2} \tau^2 \\ -\frac{1}{2} \tau^2 & \tau \end{pmatrix} \quad (71)$$

As expected, for the location the main term is just the derivative (with a minus, because we are going backwards in time).

6. Equivalence To One-Dimensional Model Through Signal-to-Noise Ratio

6.1. SNR Is All That Matters

As was shown in [3], in the one-dimensional case

$$L_{\text{diff}}^\infty = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), t \sim U[0, 1]} \mathcal{S}'_t \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \quad (72)$$

where \mathcal{S}_t is the signal-to-noise ratio. In our two-dimensional case, SNR can also be defined. For a fixed time t we can look at \mathbf{z}_t as a Gaussian vector, where each component contains signal and noise. Recall that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_t &= \boldsymbol{\alpha}_t \mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\xi}_1 \\ \mathbf{v}_t &= \boldsymbol{\lambda}_t \mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\xi}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\xi}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\xi}_2$ are Gaussian random variables with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{D}\boldsymbol{\xi}_1 &= \boldsymbol{\beta}_t \\ \mathbb{D}\boldsymbol{\xi}_2 &= \boldsymbol{\nu}_t \\ \text{cov}(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1, \boldsymbol{\xi}_2) &= \boldsymbol{\kappa}_t \end{aligned} \quad (74)$$

For simplicity we also assume $\mathbb{D}\mathbf{x} = 1$. Here \mathbf{x} is the signal.

Then there exists an optimal (Chapter 6 in [12]) linear estimate for \mathbf{x} from those two channels which we will call $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_t$:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_t = \frac{(\alpha_t \nu_t - \lambda_t \kappa_t) \mathbf{u}_t + (\beta_t \lambda_t - \alpha_t \kappa_t) \mathbf{v}_t}{(\alpha_t^2 + \beta_t)(\lambda_t^2 + \nu_t) - (\alpha_t \lambda_t + \kappa_t)^2} \quad (75)$$

The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of this estimate is also defined:

$$\mathcal{S}_t = \frac{\beta_t \lambda_t^2 + \nu_t \alpha_t^2 - 2\kappa_t \alpha_t \lambda_t}{\beta_t \nu_t - \kappa_t^2} \quad (76)$$

In Appendix F we show that, as in the one-dimensional case in [3], our smooth setting satisfies

$$L_{\text{diff}}^\infty = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), t \sim U[0, 1]} \mathcal{S}'_t \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \quad (77)$$

as well.

This has two consequences that, taken together, reframe the role of phase-space constructions in diffusion modeling.

- Re-evaluation of physical motivations. CLD ([8]) justifies its specific parameter choices through statistical-mechanics arguments: critical damping is presented as the “right” balance for smooth convergence. Equation 77 shows that, at the level of the diffusion loss, the SNR schedule is a sufficient statistic for the SDE: any two parameterizations that produce the same SNR yield the same bound. This does not invalidate empirical gains reported by CLD, but locates them outside the loss itself, for example, in score-function regularity at the boundaries or in sampler dynamics.
- Decoupling of model and process. Since \mathcal{S}_t is all that matters, a denoising model trained in the standard one-dimensional setting can be reused with any phase-space process that matches its SNR schedule, including pretrained checkpoints. Section 6.2 makes this concrete.

6.2. Turning Any Denoising Model Into Smooth Stochastic Diffusion

As was shown in the previous section, the diffusion loss depends only on SNR. This means that if any two schedules of parameters share the same SNR schedule, then the diffusion loss of those schedules will be the same (if the prediction of the denoising model is the same). Since the best linear estimate of the signal, leading to this SNR, is given by Equation 75, it makes sense to use a one-dimensional denoising model, similar to those used in classical diffusion, that will take $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_t$ as input along with a value representing SNR (we used $\log \mathcal{S}_t$ in our experiments).

The SNR schedule for training of this model can be chosen arbitrarily, given values at the endpoints. For example, we can use the one that minimizes gradient variance as in [3]. The form of the schedule does not matter in the sense that at generation time the model will still need to give predictions under any value of SNR within the chosen bounds. We can even use a pretrained model.

Independently of the model, the two-dimensional parameter schedule can be tuned to the user’s preference (the only constraint is SNR at the edges). We may want the parameters to follow a predefined SNR schedule and/or regularize them in some way, for example forcing $\alpha_0 = 1$ and $\beta_1 = 1$ as in common diffusion settings. One could strive for optimal transport ([9], [13]), or, on the contrary, make the trajectories change rapidly. We want to highlight that since the noise in \mathbf{u}_t and \mathbf{v}_t is correlated, \mathcal{S}_0 can be made very high just by increasing the correlation coefficient at $t = 0$, while having individual ratios $\frac{\alpha_0^2}{\beta_0}$ and $\frac{\lambda_0^2}{\nu_0}$ very low, so the tuning of the parameters should be done with care.

As was said earlier, the system in Equation 44 is not analytically solvable. Therefore, in our experiments we used the following setup: we initialized f_t , r_t and g_t with some neural networks that take t as input (making sure $g_t > 0$), and computed the parameters for a dense set of times via the algorithm in Appendix G, thus obtaining the whole schedule of the parameters. Then we could place some loss on the resulting schedule and optimize it using standard methods.

At generation time the procedure is as follows. We have some point $\mathbf{z}_t = (\mathbf{u}_t, \mathbf{v}_t)$ and we know the corresponding α_t , λ_t , β_t , κ_t , ν_t and g_t . We compute $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_t$ via Equation 75, which collapses \mathbf{z}_t into one

dimension and reduces the noise solely using the process parameters (without any knowledge of $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x})$). We also compute \mathcal{S}_t via Equation 76. Now $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_t$ can be rescaled to have the unit expected variance and fed to a denoising model that predicts $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)$, alongside \mathcal{S}_t (or any function of \mathcal{S}_t). That prediction is then used to construct a generative step via Equation 70.

7. Toy Experiment

To validate the correctness of the above derivations, we conducted a small experiment. $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x})$ is a mix of two two-dimensional Gaussian densities with centers at (1, 1) and (-1, -1) and standard deviations 0.1. The data is normalized so that the channel-wise standard deviation is 1. The model is a simple feed-forward network. The denoising model is trained separately using a log-linear SNR schedule with values 5 and -5 at its ends. The smooth process parameters are initialized with constraints $\alpha_0 = 1, \rho_0 = \frac{\kappa_0}{\sqrt{\beta_0 \nu_0}} = 0.5$ and trained with a loss that forces the SNR at the endpoints to be also 5 and -5 , forces $\beta_1 = 1$, and slightly regularizes the correlation coefficient so that it is not too small at every time point.

The code can be found at [github](#).

Below are the plots of the learned parameters and the SNR.

Figure 1: Plots representing the learned parameters.

The next two plots show some sample paths of one data dimension (out of two) of the generation process.

Figure 2: Generative trajectories (top) and their derivatives (bottom). The time axis is inverted, so zero corresponds to the noise distribution, and one corresponds to the data.

8. Conclusion

We presented a phase-space diffusion generative model that strictly generalizes prior velocity-augmented constructions: CLD ([8]) and AGM ([9]), by treating the SDE coefficients r_t , f_t , g_t as free time-dependent functions. In contrast to those works, which rely on score matching or bridge matching, we derived an exact ELBO through a local KL analysis and a continuous-time limit, yielding a true variational bound on $\log p(\mathbf{x})$. The central theoretical result is that, despite the additional state dimension, the diffusion loss collapses to a scalar SNR functional, which extends the SNR-only result of [3] to phase space and clarifies that trajectory smoothness, on its own, neither helps nor hurts the bound. Practically, this decoupling allows any one-dimensional denoising model (including pretrained ones) to be paired with arbitrary smooth process schedules, and we provided a parallel numerical scheme Appendix G that makes the otherwise non-analytical ODE system (Equation 44) tractable. We validated the derivations on a synthetic dataset. Scaling to image benchmarks and exploiting the ELBO for direct likelihood evaluation are the natural next steps.

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A. Gaussian Processes, Mean-Square Diminishing at Zero

For $k > 0$ define $\llbracket t^k \rrbracket$ and $\{\{t^k\}\}$ as classes of continuous processes (depending on $t \in [0, \varepsilon]$, ε being some positive constant) with globally bounded second moments such that

$$X_t \in \llbracket t^k \rrbracket \Leftrightarrow \mathbb{E}X_t^2 \stackrel{t \rightarrow 0}{=} O(t^k) \quad (78)$$

$$X_t \in \{\{t^k\}\} \Leftrightarrow \mathbb{E}X_t^2 \stackrel{t \rightarrow 0}{=} o(t^k) \quad (79)$$

If $X_t \in \llbracket t^k \rrbracket$ ($X_t \in \{\{t^k\}\}$), we will say that X_t diminishes at zero with speed (faster than) t^k in the mean-squared sense. Such processes have the following properties:

$X_t \in \llbracket t^k \rrbracket \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}^2 X_t = O(t^k)$, $\mathbb{D}X_t = O(t^k)$. This follows from $\mathbb{E}X_t^2 = \mathbb{E}^2 X_t + \mathbb{D}X_t$. Also, $|\mathbb{E}X_t| = O(t^{\frac{k}{2}})$.

$O(t^k) \subset \llbracket t^{2k} \rrbracket$. Here we loosely assume that deterministic functions are stochastic processes with zero variance everywhere.

If $X_t \in \llbracket t^k \rrbracket$ then $\forall C \in \mathbb{R}$, $CX_t \in \llbracket t^k \rrbracket$.

For Gaussian $X_t \in \llbracket t^k \rrbracket$, $Y_t \in \llbracket t^m \rrbracket$ we have $X_t Y_t \in \llbracket t^{k+m} \rrbracket$. Proof:

From the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality for X_t^2 and Y_t^2 :

$$\mathbb{E}X_t^2 Y_t^2 \leq \sqrt{\mathbb{E}X_t^4 \mathbb{E}Y_t^4} \quad (80)$$

For Gaussian variables:

$$\mathbb{E}X_t^4 = \mathbb{E}^4 X_t + 6\mathbb{E}^2 X_t \mathbb{D}X_t + 3\mathbb{D}^2 X_t = \quad (81)$$

$$O(t^{2k}) + 6O(t^k)O(t^k) + 3O(t^{2k}) = O(t^{2k}) \Rightarrow \quad (82)$$

$$\sqrt{\mathbb{E}X_t^4} = O(t^k) \quad (83)$$

Analogous for Y_t . Substituting into Equation 80 we get the result.

• $X_t \in \llbracket t^k \rrbracket$, $Y_t \in \llbracket t^m \rrbracket \Rightarrow X_t + Y_t \in \llbracket t^{\min(k,m)} \rrbracket$. Proof:

$$\mathbb{E}(X_t + Y_t)^2 = \mathbb{E}X_t^2 + 2\mathbb{E}X_t Y_t + \mathbb{E}Y_t^2 \leq (\text{Cauchy-Schwarz}) \quad (84)$$

$$\mathbb{E}X_t^2 + 2\sqrt{\mathbb{E}X_t^2 \mathbb{E}Y_t^2} + \mathbb{E}Y_t^2 = \quad (85)$$

$$O(t^k) + 2\sqrt{O(t^k)O(t^m)} + O(t^m) = \quad (86)$$

$$O(t^k) + O(t^{\frac{k+m}{2}}) + O(t^m) = \quad (87)$$

$$O(t^{\min(k,m)}) \quad (88)$$

(All of the above is analogous for $\{\{t^k\}\}$ and $o(t^m)$)

• $\{\{t^k\}\} \subset \llbracket t^k \rrbracket$.

• $X_t \in \llbracket t^k \rrbracket$, $Y_t \in \llbracket t^m \rrbracket \Rightarrow \text{cov}(X_t, Y_t) = O(t^{\frac{k+m}{2}})$. Proof:

$$\text{cov}(X_t, Y_t) = \mathbb{E}((X_t - \mathbb{E}[X_t])(Y_t - \mathbb{E}[Y_t])) = \mathbb{E}X_t Y_t - \mathbb{E}X_t \mathbb{E}Y_t \quad (89)$$

$$|\mathbb{E}X_t Y_t - \mathbb{E}X_t \mathbb{E}Y_t| \leq |\mathbb{E}X_t Y_t| + |\mathbb{E}X_t| \cdot |\mathbb{E}Y_t| \leq \quad (90)$$

$$\sqrt{\mathbb{E}X_t^2 \mathbb{E}Y_t^2} + |\mathbb{E}X_t| \cdot |\mathbb{E}Y_t| = \quad (91)$$

$$\sqrt{O(t^k)O(t^m)} + |O(t^{\frac{k}{2}})| \cdot |O(t^{\frac{m}{2}})| = O(t^{\frac{k+m}{2}}) \quad (92)$$

We will also need the properties of integrals of such processes.

Let $X_t \in \llbracket t^k \rrbracket$. Let's look at the second moment of its integral:

$$\mathbb{E} \left(\int_0^t X_s ds \right)^2 = \quad (93)$$

$$\mathbb{E} \left(\int_0^t \int_0^t X_r X_s dr ds \right) = \quad (94)$$

$$\int_0^t \int_0^t \mathbb{E} X_r X_s dr ds \leq \quad (95)$$

(Cauchy-Schwarz)

$$\int_0^t \int_0^t \max(\mathbb{E} X_r^2, \mathbb{E} X_s^2) dr ds \leq \quad (96)$$

$$\int_0^t \int_0^t \max_{u \in [0; t]} \mathbb{E} X_u^2 dr ds = \quad (97)$$

$$\max_{u \in [0; t]} \mathbb{E} X_u^2 \int_0^t \int_0^t 1 dr ds = \quad (98)$$

$$\max_{u \in [0; t]} \mathbb{E} X_u^2 t^2 \quad (99)$$

By definition of O -notation, $\exists C > 0$, such that $\forall t > 0$

$$\mathbb{E} X_t^2 \leq C t^k \quad (100)$$

Therefore,

$$\max_{u \in [0; t]} \mathbb{E} X_u^2 \leq C t^k \quad (101)$$

So we get

$$\mathbb{E} \left(\int_0^t X_s ds \right)^2 \leq C t^{k+2} \quad (102)$$

which means $\int_0^t X_s ds \in \llbracket t^{k+2} \rrbracket$.

Analogously for $\llbracket t^k \rrbracket$.

B. Inference of Posterior Parameters

Suppose we have a Gaussian process with marginal distribution $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_t)$ (perhaps conditioned on \mathbf{x}), with mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}_t$ and covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_t$. Let $\tau = t - s$ and let the forward transition probability $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_t | \mathbf{z}_s)$ have the mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s} = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{z}_s$ and covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t|s}$. Also, let the backward transition probability $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_s | \mathbf{z}_t)$ have the mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t}$ and covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s|t}$.

By Bayes rule:

$$\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_s | \mathbf{z}_t) = \frac{\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_t | \mathbf{z}_s) \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_s)}{\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_t)} \Rightarrow \quad (103)$$

$$\log \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_s | \mathbf{z}_t) = \log \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_t | \mathbf{z}_s) + \log \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_s) - \log (\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{z}_t)) \Rightarrow \quad (104)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \log \left(\frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{n}{2}} (\det \Sigma_{s|t})^{\frac{1}{2}}} \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t})^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t}) \right) \right) = \\ & \log \left(\frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{n}{2}} (\det \Sigma_{t|s})^{\frac{1}{2}}} \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s})^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s}) \right) \right) + \end{aligned} \quad (105)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \log \left(\frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{n}{2}} (\det \Sigma_s)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s)^T \Sigma_s^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s) \right) \right) - \\ & \log \left(\frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{n}{2}} (\det \Sigma_t)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_t)^T \Sigma_t^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_t) \right) \right) \Rightarrow \\ & -\frac{n}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \log(\det \Sigma_{s|t}) - \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t})^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t}) = \\ & -\frac{n}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \log(\det \Sigma_{t|s}) - \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s})^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s}) + \end{aligned} \quad (106)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{n}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \log(\det \Sigma_s) - \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s)^T \Sigma_s^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s) + \\ & \frac{n}{2} \log(2\pi) + \frac{1}{2} \log(\det \Sigma_t) + \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_t)^T \Sigma_t^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_t) \Rightarrow \\ & \log(\det \Sigma_{s|t}) + (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t})^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t}) = \\ & \log(\det \Sigma_{t|s}) + (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s})^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s}) + \\ & + \log(\det \Sigma_s) + (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s)^T \Sigma_s^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s) - \\ & -\log(\det \Sigma_t) - (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_t)^T \Sigma_t^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_t) \end{aligned} \quad (107)$$

We will look at this expression as a function of \mathbf{z}_s , so all constants are going to be hidden in C :

$$\begin{aligned} & (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t})^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t}) + C_1 = \\ & (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s})^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s}) + (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s)^T \Sigma_s^{-1} (\mathbf{z}_s - \boldsymbol{\mu}_s) + C_2 \Rightarrow \end{aligned} \quad (108)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} \mathbf{z}_s - 2\mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} + C_1 = \\ & \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s} - 2\mathbf{z}_t^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{t|s} + \mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_s^{-1} \mathbf{z}_s - 2\mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s + C_2 \Rightarrow \end{aligned} \quad (109)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} \mathbf{z}_s - 2\mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} + C_1 = \\ & (\mathbf{H}\mathbf{z}_s)^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{z}_s - 2\mathbf{z}_t^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{z}_s + \mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_s^{-1} \mathbf{z}_s - 2\mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s + C_2 \Rightarrow \end{aligned} \quad (110)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} \mathbf{z}_s - 2\mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} + C_1 = \\ & \mathbf{z}_s^T \mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{z}_s - 2\mathbf{z}_t^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{z}_s + \mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_s^{-1} \mathbf{z}_s - 2\mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s + C_2 \Rightarrow \end{aligned} \quad (111)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} \mathbf{z}_s - 2\mathbf{z}_s^T \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} + C_1 = \\ & \mathbf{z}_s^T (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H} + \Sigma_s^{-1}) \mathbf{z}_s - 2\mathbf{z}_s^T (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_t + \Sigma_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s) + C_2 \end{aligned} \quad (112)$$

From the functional form of expressions we get that $C_1 = C_2$ and

$$\Sigma_{s|t} = (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H} + \Sigma_s^{-1})^{-1} \quad (113)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} = \Sigma_{s|t} (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_t + \Sigma_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s) \quad (114)$$

C. Matrix Main Terms

Consider a class of matrices that contains all matrices $A = A(\tau)$ such that each element of A is a rational function of τ (a fraction of two polynomials of τ).

Then the linear operations on matrices, multiplication, and the inverse (if defined) are closed in this class.

Any rational function $f(\tau)$ can be represented as (assuming $\tau \rightarrow 0$):

$$f(\tau) = C\tau^k + o(\tau^k) \quad (115)$$

where $k \in \mathbb{Z}$. If $f(\tau) \equiv 0$, then we assume $C = 0$. Otherwise, $C \neq 0$.

If a matrix A belongs to the above class, then we define $[A]$ as the matrix in which each element contains only the leading term of the corresponding element of A (the term $C\tau^k$ from Equation 115).

Now we will list some properties of the operation $[\cdot]$ relative to regular matrix operations. For simplicity (and for the use in this paper) we will use 2×2 matrices. Let

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \begin{pmatrix} a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{11}}) & a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{12}}) \\ a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{21}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{21}}) & a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{22}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{22}}) \end{pmatrix}, \\ B &= \begin{pmatrix} b_{11}\tau^{\beta_{11}} + o(\tau^{\beta_{11}}) & b_{12}\tau^{\beta_{12}} + o(\tau^{\beta_{12}}) \\ b_{21}\tau^{\beta_{21}} + o(\tau^{\beta_{21}}) & b_{22}\tau^{\beta_{22}} + o(\tau^{\beta_{22}}) \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad (116)$$

- $[[A]] = [A]$
- $\forall c \in \mathbb{R}, c \neq 0, [cA] = c[A]$
- $[A + B] = [[A] + [B]]$ if all elements of $[[A] + [B]]$ are non-zero.

Since addition is element-wise, it will be enough to check only the sum of one element.

$$[A_{11}] = a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} \quad (117)$$

$$[B_{11}] = b_{11}\tau^{\beta_{11}} \quad (118)$$

$$A_{11} + B_{11} = a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{11}}) + b_{11}\tau^{\beta_{11}} + o(\tau^{\beta_{11}}) \quad (119)$$

If $\alpha_{11} < \beta_{11}$ (the opposite is analogous), then $B_{11} = o(A_{11})$ and the result is

$$a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{11}}) \quad (120)$$

so

$$[A_{11} + B_{11}] = a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} \quad (121)$$

On the other hand,

$$[[A_{11}] + [B_{11}]] = [a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} + b_{11}\tau^{\beta_{11}}] = a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} \quad (122)$$

so the equality holds.

If $\alpha_{11} = \beta_{11}$, then the result is

$$(a_{11} + b_{11})\tau^{\alpha_{11}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{11}}) \quad (123)$$

Suppose $a_{11} + b_{11} \neq 0$. Then:

$$[A_{11} + B_{11}] = (a_{11} + b_{11})\tau^{\alpha_{11}} \quad (124)$$

On the other hand,

$$[[A_{11}] + [B_{11}]] = [a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} + b_{11}\tau^{\beta_{11}}] = (a_{11} + b_{11})\tau^{\alpha_{11}} \quad (125)$$

so the equality holds.

If, however, $a_{11} + b_{11} = 0$, then $(a_{11} + b_{11})\tau^{\alpha_{11}}$ will not be the main term. Some term from $o(\tau^{\alpha_{11}})$ will become the main term. So we can say that the equality holds only if all elements of $[[A] + [B]]$ are **nonzero**.

- $[AB] = [[A]B]$ if all elements of $[[A]B]$ are non-zero

It will be enough to look only at the top left element of the result:

$$\begin{aligned} & A_{11}B_{11} + A_{12}B_{21} = \\ & (a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{11}}))(b_{11}\tau^{\beta_{11}} + o(\tau^{\beta_{11}})) + (a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{12}}))(b_{21}\tau^{\beta_{21}} + o(\tau^{\beta_{21}})) = \quad (126) \\ & a_{11}b_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}+\beta_{11}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{11}+\beta_{11}}) + a_{12}b_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{12}+\beta_{21}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{12}+\beta_{21}}) \end{aligned}$$

Right side:

$$\begin{aligned} & [A_{11}]B_{11} + [A_{12}]B_{21} = \\ & a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}}(b_{11}\tau^{\beta_{11}} + o(\tau^{\beta_{11}})) + a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}}(b_{21}\tau^{\beta_{21}} + o(\tau^{\beta_{21}})) = \quad (127) \\ & a_{11}b_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}+\beta_{11}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{11}+\beta_{11}}) + a_{12}b_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{12}+\beta_{21}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{12}+\beta_{21}}) \end{aligned}$$

The main parts of the sides are equal if either $\alpha_{11} + \beta_{11} \neq \alpha_{12} + \beta_{21}$ or if $a_{11}b_{11} + a_{12}b_{21} \neq 0$. So again the equality holds only if all elements of $[[A]B]$ are non-zero.

Equation

- $[AB] = [[A][B]]$ if all elements of $[[A][B]]$ are non-zero

follows.

- $[A^{-1}] = [[A]^{-1}]$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} & A^{-1} = \\ & \begin{pmatrix} a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{11}}) & a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{12}}) \\ a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{21}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{21}}) & a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{22}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{22}}) \end{pmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}}(1 + o(1)) & a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}}(1 + o(1)) \\ a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{21}}(1 + o(1)) & a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{22}}(1 + o(1)) \end{pmatrix}^{-1} = \quad (128) \\ & \frac{1}{a_{11}a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{11}+\alpha_{22}}(1 + o(1)) - a_{12}a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{12}+\alpha_{21}}(1 + o(1))} \begin{pmatrix} a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{22}}(1 + o(1)) & -a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}}(1 + o(1)) \\ -a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{21}}(1 + o(1)) & a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}}(1 + o(1)) \end{pmatrix} \quad (129) \\ & = \frac{1}{(a_{11}a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{11}+\alpha_{22}} - a_{12}a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{12}+\alpha_{21}})(1 + o(1))} \begin{pmatrix} a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{22}}(1 + o(1)) & -a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}}(1 + o(1)) \\ -a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{21}}(1 + o(1)) & a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}}(1 + o(1)) \end{pmatrix} \quad (130) \end{aligned}$$

(Here we did not, of course, just put $(1 + o(1))$ outside the brackets in the denominator, because the concrete functions could be different, but the equality still holds. Now we fuse the bracket in the denominator with the ones in the numerator.)

$$= \frac{1}{(a_{11}a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{11}+\alpha_{22}} - a_{12}a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{12}+\alpha_{21}})} \begin{pmatrix} a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{22}}(1 + o(1)) & -a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}}(1 + o(1)) \\ -a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{21}}(1 + o(1)) & a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}}(1 + o(1)) \end{pmatrix} = \quad (131)$$

$$\frac{1}{(a_{11}a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{11}+\alpha_{22}} - a_{12}a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{12}+\alpha_{21}})} \begin{pmatrix} a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{22}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{22}}) & -a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{12}}) \\ -a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{21}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{21}}) & a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} + o(\tau^{\alpha_{11}}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (132)$$

So

$$\begin{aligned} & [A^{-1}] = \\ & \left[\frac{1}{(a_{11}a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{11}+\alpha_{22}} - a_{12}a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{12}+\alpha_{21}})} \begin{pmatrix} a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{22}} & -a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}} \\ -a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{21}} & a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} \end{pmatrix} \right] \quad (133) \end{aligned}$$

The actual value depends on the relation between $\alpha_{11} + \alpha_{22}$ and $\alpha_{12} + \alpha_{21}$. The main part of the determinant must be nonzero.

Now, knowing that

$$[A]^{-1} = \frac{1}{(a_{11}a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{11}+\alpha_{22}} - a_{12}a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{12}+\alpha_{21}})} \begin{pmatrix} a_{22}\tau^{\alpha_{22}} & -a_{12}\tau^{\alpha_{12}} \\ -a_{21}\tau^{\alpha_{21}} & a_{11}\tau^{\alpha_{11}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (134)$$

we get the result.

D. Main Term of Diffusion Loss

Since in the $\mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(s)$ only $\Sigma_{s|t}$ depends on τ , then:

$$[\mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(s)] = \left[\frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\theta}(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \left(\Sigma_s^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_s \\ \lambda_s \end{pmatrix} \right)^T [\Sigma_{s|t}] \left(\Sigma_s^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_s \\ \lambda_s \end{pmatrix} \right) \right] \quad (135)$$

Let's look at the main part of $\Sigma_{s|t}$:

$$[\Sigma_{s|t}] = \left[(\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H} + \Sigma_s^{-1})^{-1} \right] \quad (136)$$

Step-by-step:

$$[\mathbf{H}] = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \tau \\ -r_s \tau & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (137)$$

$$[\Sigma_{t|s}^{-1}] = \left[[\Sigma_{t|s}]^{-1} \right] = \frac{1}{g_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{12}{\tau^3} & -\frac{6}{\tau^2} \\ -\frac{6}{\tau^2} & \frac{4}{\tau} \end{pmatrix} \quad (138)$$

$$\Sigma_s^{-1} = \frac{1}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_s & -\kappa_s \\ -\kappa_s & \beta_s \end{pmatrix} \quad (139)$$

This means, that Σ_s^{-1} is dominated by $\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H}$, so

$$[\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H} + \Sigma_s^{-1}] = [\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H}] \quad (140)$$

Now we can apply the following transition (see Appendix C):

$$\begin{aligned} [\Sigma_{s|t}] &= \left[(\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H} + \Sigma_s^{-1})^{-1} \right] = \left[[\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H} + \Sigma_s^{-1}]^{-1} \right] = \left[[\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H}]^{-1} \right] = \\ &= \left[[\mathbf{H}^T] [\Sigma_{t|s}^{-1}] [\mathbf{H}]^{-1} \right] = \left[[\mathbf{H}^{-1}] [\Sigma_{t|s}] [\mathbf{H}^{-T}] \right] \end{aligned} \quad (141)$$

Calculating:

$$[\mathbf{H}]^{-1} = \frac{1}{1 + r_s \tau^2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\tau \\ r_s \tau & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (142)$$

So,

$$[[\mathbf{H}]^{-1}] = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\tau \\ r_s \tau & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (143)$$

Then

$$[[\mathbf{H}]^{-1} [\Sigma_{t|s}] [\mathbf{H}^{-T}]] = g_s^2 \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3} \tau^3 & -\frac{1}{2} \tau^2 \\ -\frac{1}{2} \tau^2 & \tau \end{pmatrix} \quad (144)$$

So $\mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(s)$ becomes

$$[\mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(s)] = \frac{g_s^2}{2} \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\theta}(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \left(\Sigma_s^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_s \\ \lambda_s \end{pmatrix} \right)^T \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3} \tau^3 & -\frac{1}{2} \tau^2 \\ -\frac{1}{2} \tau^2 & \tau \end{pmatrix} \left(\Sigma_s^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_s \\ \lambda_s \end{pmatrix} \right) \quad (145)$$

We can immediately see, that the result of multiplication will have τ in its main term. The coefficient of this term is the bottom element of $\Sigma_s^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_s \\ \lambda_s \end{pmatrix}$ squared.

$$\Sigma_s^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_s \\ \lambda_s \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_s & -\kappa_s \\ -\kappa_s & \beta_s \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_s \\ \lambda_s \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_s \nu_s - \kappa_s \lambda_s \\ -\alpha_s \kappa_s + \beta_s \lambda_s \end{pmatrix} \quad (146)$$

So we get

$$[\mathbf{D}_{\text{KL}}(s)] = \tau \frac{g_s^2}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha_s \kappa_s - \beta_s \lambda_s}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \right)^2 \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \quad (147)$$

E. Main Term of Generative Step

Main term of step:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} - \mathbf{z}_t &= \Sigma_{s|t} (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{z}_t + \Sigma_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s) - \mathbf{z}_t = \\ &= (\Sigma_{s|t} \mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} - I) \mathbf{z}_t + \Sigma_{s|t} \Sigma_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s \end{aligned} \quad (148)$$

Rearranging the multiplier before \mathbf{z}_t :

$$\begin{aligned} (\Sigma_{s|t} \mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} - I) &= (\Sigma_{s|t} \mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} - \Sigma_{s|t} \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1}) = \\ &= \Sigma_{s|t} (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} - \Sigma_{s|t}^{-1}) = \\ &= \Sigma_{s|t} (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} - (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \mathbf{H} + \Sigma_s^{-1})) = \\ &= \Sigma_{s|t} (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} (I - \mathbf{H}) - \Sigma_s^{-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (149)$$

Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} - \mathbf{z}_t &= \Sigma_{s|t} (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} (I - \mathbf{H}) - \Sigma_s^{-1}) \mathbf{z}_t + \Sigma_{s|t} \Sigma_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s = \\ &= \Sigma_{s|t} \mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} (I - \mathbf{H}) \mathbf{z}_t + \Sigma_{s|t} \Sigma_s^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \mathbf{z}_t) = \\ &= \Sigma_{s|t} (\mathbf{H}^T \Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} (I - \mathbf{H}) \mathbf{z}_t + \Sigma_s^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \mathbf{z}_t)) \end{aligned} \quad (150)$$

Taking the main term:

$$\begin{aligned} [\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s|t} - \mathbf{z}_t] &= \\ &= \left[\left[\Sigma_{s|t} \right] \left[\mathbf{H}^T \right] \left[\Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \right] \left[I - \mathbf{H} \right] \mathbf{z}_t + \Sigma_s^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \mathbf{z}_t) \right] = \\ &= \left[\mathbf{H}^{-1} \right] \left[\Sigma_{t|s} \right] \left[\mathbf{H}^{-T} \right] \left[\mathbf{H}^T \right] \left[\Sigma_{t|s}^{-1} \right] \left[I - \mathbf{H} \right] \mathbf{z}_t + \Sigma_s^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \mathbf{z}_t) \right] = \\ &= \left[\mathbf{H}^{-1} \right] \left[I - \mathbf{H} \right] \mathbf{z}_t + \left[\mathbf{H}^{-1} \right] \left[\Sigma_{t|s} \right] \left[\mathbf{H}^{-T} \right] \Sigma_s^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \mathbf{z}_t) \end{aligned} \quad (151)$$

Let's look at the parts:

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\mathbf{H}^{-1} \right] \left[I - \mathbf{H} \right] &= \\ &= \left[\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\tau \\ r_s \tau & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} r_s \tau^2 & -\tau \\ r_s \tau & f_s \tau \end{pmatrix} \right] = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} r_s \tau^2 & -\tau \\ r_s \tau & f_s \tau \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (152)$$

So:

$$\left[\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} r_s \tau^2 & -\tau \\ r_s \tau & f_s \tau \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{z}_t \right] = \begin{pmatrix} -\tau \mathbf{v}_t \\ \tau (r_s \mathbf{u}_t + f_s \mathbf{v}_t) \end{pmatrix} \quad (153)$$

Next,

$$\begin{aligned}
[\mathbf{H}^{-1}][\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{t,s}][\mathbf{H}^{-T}]\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} &= \begin{bmatrix} g_s^2 \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3}\tau^3 & -\frac{1}{2}\tau^2 \\ -\frac{1}{2}\tau^2 & \tau \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_s & -\kappa_s \\ -\kappa_s & \beta_s \end{pmatrix} \\ \frac{g_s^2}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\kappa_s}{2}\tau^2 & -\frac{\beta_s}{2}\tau^2 \\ -\kappa_s \tau & \beta_s \tau \end{pmatrix} \end{bmatrix} = \\
& \frac{g_s^2}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\kappa_s}{2}\tau^2 & -\frac{\beta_s}{2}\tau^2 \\ -\kappa_s \tau & \beta_s \tau \end{pmatrix} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \mathbf{z}_t) = \\
& \frac{g_s^2}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\tau^2}{2}(\kappa_s(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{u}_t) - \beta_s(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{v}_t)) \\ \tau(-\kappa_s(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{u}_t) + \beta_s(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{v}_t)) \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned} \tag{154}$$

So:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[\frac{g_s^2}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\kappa_s}{2}\tau^2 & -\frac{\beta_s}{2}\tau^2 \\ -\kappa_s \tau & \beta_s \tau \end{pmatrix} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s - \mathbf{z}_t) \right] = \\
& \frac{g_s^2}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\tau^2}{2}(\kappa_s(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{u}_t) - \beta_s(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{v}_t)) \\ \tau(-\kappa_s(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{u}_t) + \beta_s(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{v}_t)) \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned} \tag{155}$$

And the sum:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[\begin{pmatrix} -\tau \mathbf{v}_t \\ \tau(r_s \mathbf{u}_t + f_s \mathbf{v}_t) \end{pmatrix} + \frac{g_s^2}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\tau^2}{2}(\kappa_s(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{u}_t) - \beta_s(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{v}_t)) \\ \tau(-\kappa_s(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{u}_t) + \beta_s(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{v}_t)) \end{pmatrix} \right] = \\
& \tau \begin{pmatrix} -\mathbf{v}_t \\ r_s \mathbf{u}_t + f_s \mathbf{v}_t + \frac{g_s^2}{\beta_s \nu_s - \kappa_s^2} (-\kappa_s(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{u}_t) + \beta_s(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_s \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t) - \mathbf{v}_t)) \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned} \tag{156}$$

F. Derivative of SNR in Two-Dimensional Case

For this proof we will drop the time index t . All derivatives are taken with respect to t .

$$\mathcal{S} = \frac{\beta \lambda^2 + \nu \alpha^2 - 2\kappa \alpha \lambda}{\beta \nu - \kappa^2} \tag{157}$$

We will denote the numerator and denominator of \mathcal{S} as \mathcal{S}_{num} and $\mathcal{S}_{\text{denom}}$. Then,

$$\mathcal{S}' = \frac{\mathcal{S}'_{\text{num}} \mathcal{S}_{\text{denom}} - \mathcal{S}_{\text{num}} \mathcal{S}'_{\text{denom}}}{\mathcal{S}_{\text{denom}}^2} \tag{158}$$

By parts:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{S}'_{\text{num}} &= \beta' \lambda^2 + 2\beta \lambda \lambda' + \nu' \alpha^2 + 2\nu \alpha \lambda - 2\kappa' \alpha \lambda - 2\kappa \lambda^2 - 2\kappa \alpha \lambda' = \\
& 2\beta \lambda \lambda' + \nu' \alpha^2 + 2\nu \alpha \lambda - 2\kappa' \alpha \lambda - 2\kappa \alpha \lambda' = \\
& 2\lambda'(\beta \lambda - \kappa \alpha) + \nu' \alpha^2 + 2\nu \alpha \lambda - 2\kappa' \alpha \lambda = \\
& 2\lambda'(\beta \lambda - \kappa \alpha) + \nu' \alpha^2 + 2\alpha \lambda(\nu - \kappa') = \\
& 2\lambda'(\beta \lambda - \kappa \alpha) + \nu' \alpha^2 + 2\alpha \lambda(f\kappa + r\beta) = \\
& -2(f\lambda + r\alpha)(\beta \lambda - \kappa \alpha) + (g^2 - 2f\nu - 2r\kappa)\alpha^2 + 2\alpha \lambda(f\kappa + r\beta) = \\
2(-f\beta \lambda^2 - r\alpha \beta \lambda + f\lambda \kappa \alpha + r\kappa \alpha^2) &+ (g^2 - 2f\nu - 2r\kappa)\alpha^2 + 2\alpha \lambda(f\kappa + r\beta) = \\
& -2f\beta \lambda^2 + (g^2 - 2f\nu)\alpha^2 + 4\alpha \lambda f\kappa = \\
& -2f\beta \lambda^2 + g^2 \alpha^2 - 2f\nu \alpha^2 + 4\alpha \lambda f\kappa = \\
& g^2 \alpha^2 - 2f(\beta \lambda^2 + \nu \alpha^2 - 2\alpha \lambda \kappa) = \\
& g^2 \alpha^2 - 2f \mathcal{S}_{\text{num}}
\end{aligned} \tag{159}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{S}'_{\text{denom}} &= \beta' \nu + \beta \nu' - 2\kappa \kappa' = \\
2\kappa \nu + \beta(g^2 - 2f\nu - 2r\kappa) - 2\kappa(\nu - f\kappa - r\beta) &= \\
\beta(g^2 - 2f\nu) + 2f\kappa^2 &= \\
\beta g^2 - 2f(\beta\nu - \kappa^2) &= \\
\beta g^2 - 2f\mathcal{S}_{\text{denom}} &
\end{aligned} \tag{160}$$

Together:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{S}' &= \frac{(g^2\alpha^2 - 2f\mathcal{S}_{\text{num}})\mathcal{S}_{\text{denom}} - (\beta g^2 - 2f\mathcal{S}_{\text{denom}})\mathcal{S}_{\text{num}}}{\mathcal{S}_{\text{denom}}^2} = \\
&= \frac{g^2\alpha^2\mathcal{S}_{\text{denom}} - \beta\mathcal{S}_{\text{num}}}{\mathcal{S}_{\text{denom}}^2} = \\
&= \frac{g^2\alpha^2(\beta\nu - \kappa^2) - \beta(\beta\lambda^2 + \nu\alpha^2 - 2\kappa\alpha\lambda)}{(\beta\nu - \kappa^2)^2} = \\
&= \frac{g^2 - \alpha^2\kappa^2 + 2\alpha\kappa\beta\lambda - \beta^2\lambda^2}{(\beta\nu - \kappa^2)^2} = \\
&= -g^2 \left(\frac{\alpha\kappa - \beta\lambda}{\beta\nu - \kappa^2} \right)^2
\end{aligned} \tag{161}$$

So we get

$$L_{\text{diff}}^\infty = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}_{\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), t \sim U[0, 1]} \mathcal{S}'_t \|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)\|_2^2 \tag{162}$$

G. Fast Numerical Solution of Process Parameters

We have a set of ODEs

$$\begin{cases} \alpha'_t = \lambda_t \\ \lambda'_t = -f_t \lambda_t - r_t \alpha_t \\ \beta'_t = 2\kappa_t \\ \kappa'_t = \nu_t - f_t \kappa_t - r_t \beta_t \\ \nu'_t = g_t^2 - 2f_t \nu_t - 2r_t \kappa_t \end{cases} \tag{163}$$

Let $\varphi_t = (\alpha_t, \lambda_t, \beta_t, \kappa_t, \nu_t, 1)$, with φ_0 being the initial conditions. The 1 at the end will be used for biases. We want to find the values of φ_t for t belonging to some (in our case evenly spaced) discretization $[0, \Delta t, 2\Delta t, \dots, 1]$ of $[0, 1]$. In our experiments we used $N = 4096$ points. The following algorithm will be presented for the special case when the number of points is a power of two.

Suppose we can evaluate f_t, r_t , and g_t quickly and in parallel for all points in the discretization. This is the case, for example, if those functions are modelled as neural networks.

If

$$A_t = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -r_t & -f_t & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -r_t & -f_t & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -2r_t & -2f_t & g_t^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \tag{164}$$

Then, the iteration of the Euler method can be written as

$$\varphi_{t+\Delta t} = (I + \Delta t A_t) \varphi_t = \tilde{A}_t \varphi_t \tag{165}$$

So for any point in time after some number of iterations n we get

$$\varphi_{n\Delta t} = \left(\prod_{i=0}^{n-1} \tilde{A}_{i\Delta t} \right) \varphi_0 \quad (166)$$

All of the matrices $\tilde{A}_{i\Delta t}$ can be constructed in parallel. Now we want to evaluate all cumulative products of $\tilde{A}_{i\Delta t}$ times φ_0 , thus obtaining the values of the parameters of the process for all times in the discretization.

Let

$$\tilde{A}_{i \rightarrow j} = \prod_{k=i}^j \tilde{A}_{k\Delta t} \quad (167)$$

Since matrix multiplication is an associative operation,

$$\tilde{A}_{i \rightarrow j} \tilde{A}_{j \rightarrow l} = \tilde{A}_{i \rightarrow l} \quad (168)$$

We start with an array of matrices

$$\mathcal{A}_0 = (\tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow 0}, \tilde{A}_{1 \rightarrow 1}, \dots, \tilde{A}_{i \rightarrow i}, \dots, \tilde{A}_{N \rightarrow N}) \quad (169)$$

Now if we reshape the tensor and multiply each pair of elements, we get

$$\mathcal{A}_1 = (\tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow 1}, \tilde{A}_{2 \rightarrow 3}, \dots, \tilde{A}_{i \rightarrow i+1}, \dots, \tilde{A}_{N-1 \rightarrow N}) \quad (170)$$

The size of the tensor is now halved. Repeating this operation $\log_2 N$ times we get the final states.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_{\log_2 N - 2} &= (\dots, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow \frac{N}{4}}, \tilde{A}_{\frac{N}{4} \rightarrow \frac{N}{2}}, \tilde{A}_{\frac{N}{2} \rightarrow 3\frac{N}{4}}, \tilde{A}_{3\frac{N}{4} \rightarrow N}) \\ \mathcal{A}_{\log_2 N - 1} &= (\tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow \frac{N}{2}}, \tilde{A}_{\frac{N}{2} \rightarrow N}) \\ \mathcal{A}_{\log_2 N} &= (\tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow N}) \end{aligned} \quad (171)$$

Now, to obtain the cumulative products with φ_0 we will walk back on the results in the reverse direction.

We start with $\mathcal{P}_0 = (\varphi_0)$. Multiplying this vector with the first element from $\mathcal{A}_{\log_2 N - 1}$ and keeping φ_0 we get

$$\mathcal{P}_1 = (\varphi_0, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow \frac{N}{2}} \varphi_0) \quad (172)$$

Now we take every second element of $\mathcal{A}_{\log_2 N - 2}$, starting from the first, and multiply them with the corresponding elements in \mathcal{P}_1 . The result is concatenated with the elements in \mathcal{P}_1 :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_2 &= (\varphi_0, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow \frac{N}{4}} \varphi_0, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow \frac{N}{2}} \varphi_0, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow \frac{N}{2}} \tilde{A}_{\frac{N}{2} \rightarrow 3\frac{N}{4}} \varphi_0) = \\ &= (\varphi_0, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow \frac{N}{4}} \varphi_0, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow \frac{N}{2}} \varphi_0, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow 3\frac{N}{4}} \varphi_0) \end{aligned} \quad (173)$$

On each of the following iterations we will use every second element from \mathcal{A}_i starting from the first, multiply them with the corresponding elements in \mathcal{P}_{i-1} , and concatenate with \mathcal{P}_{i-1} followed by rearrangement.

After the last iteration we get

$$\mathcal{P}_{\log_2 N} = (\varphi_0, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow 1} \varphi_0, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow 2} \varphi_0, \dots, \tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow N-1} \varphi_0) \quad (174)$$

The only missing element is $\tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow N} \varphi_0$ which we can compute, since $\tilde{A}_{0 \rightarrow n}$ is the only element of $\mathcal{A}_{\log_2 N}$.

Now we will briefly discuss the time complexity of the algorithm above. The sequential method needs to compute N matrix-vector products one after another. Our algorithm needs to perform $\log_2 N$ iterations of parallel matrix-matrix products plus $\log_2 N$ iterations of parallel matrix-vector products + some constant operations. If we assume infinite parallelization, then the speedup is from N -linear to N -

logarithmic time. We want to point out that this approach is suitable only for relatively small matrices, since our algorithm uses matrix-matrix products, while the sequential one relies only on matrix-vector products.

In practice we observe up to a $\times 20$ speedup compared to the sequential matrix-vector product evaluation in our setup (6×6 matrix, 4096 time points, Nvidia RTX 3070 GPU).

We did not investigate the numerical stability of this method.